

Assessment of Rice Mill Effluent Contamination on Drinking Water Quality in Kebbi, Nigeria

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Abstract

Wastewater discharged from rice processing mills increasingly poses environmental and health risks. They distort water quality and increase biological activity. This study assessed the physicochemical characteristics, mineral elements and heavy metal composition of wastewater from two rice processing mills (EX: effluent wastewater from factory X and EY: effluent wastewater from factory Y) and drinking water sources around the effluent discharge sites (DWX: Drinking water from water sources around factory X and DWY: Drinking water from water sources around factory Y) in Birnin Kebbi metropolis. The outcomes indicated significantly elevated levels ($p < 0.05$) of electrical conductivity (EC) and total dissolved solids (TDS) of effluent wastewater in comparison to drinking water. The highest EC was observed in EX (3932.00 ± 538.54 S/m), this was followed by the EC of EY (2545.60 ± 90.23 S/m). The ECs of drinking water from the effluents discharge sites were 294.20 ± 18.42 S/m and 85.60 ± 6.84 S/m for DWX and DWY respectively. The TDS of EX and EY (1962.20 ± 268.77 mg/L and 1268.80 ± 40.29 mg/L) were comparatively higher than that of their corresponding drinking water samples; DWX and DWY (146.40 ± 9.15 mg/L and 43.00 ± 3.08 mg/L respectively). The pH and temperature of the tested samples indicated no significant difference ($p > 0.05$). The pH ranged from 5.81 to 7.86, while temperature ranged from 26.02 to 28.20°C. Amongst mineral elements, K was highest, followed by Na and then Ca. Moderately low levels of Mg and Mn were observed in all samples. The levels of Fe and Mn in effluent wastewater were above the WHO recommended limits of ≤ 0.3 and 0.40 mg/L for Fe and Mn respectively. Except for Cr and Pb, all the analysed heavy metal were below WHO recommended limits. Rice effluent discharge was observed to distort water quality, thus reinforcement the need for stringent environmental monitoring and control.

Keywords: Birnin Kebbi, Drinking water, Effluents, Heavy metals, Rice mills, Wastewater, Water quality

1.0 Introduction

Environmental pollution arising from industrial effluent discharge is a growing concern globally, particularly in agrarian economies such as Nigeria, where unregulated industrial processes contribute significantly to ecological degradation. Rice milling, a dominant agro-industrial activity in Kebbi State, generates large volumes of wastewater that are typically discharged untreated into near by water bodies and agricultural lands.

These effluents contain complex mixtures of organic matter, suspended solids, and toxic heavy metals, all of which reduce water quality and pose risks to soil fertility [1,2].

It is a common practice for rice mills and other small industries to discharge effluents into near by wetlands, lakes, canals, rivers, crop fields, etc. During the rainy season, these contaminated waters are frequently used for irrigation, thereby transferring toxic elements from water into soil

and food crops. In this way, pollutants easily enter the food chain, posing threats to human health, ecosystems, agricultural productivity, and overall food security [3]. Rice mill effluents may also contain pathogenic microorganisms and toxic chemicals that constitute health hazards. Prolonged exposure to such polluted water has been linked to chronic illnesses, including kidney damage, neurological disorders, cardiovascular diseases and certain types of cancer [4]. In Birnin Kebbi Metropolis, the increasing number of rice mills has not been matched with investment in wastewater treatment infrastructure. Consequently, communities located around rice mills are exposed to untreated wastewater on a daily basis. Previous studies carried out in other parts of Nigeria, such as Ogun and Ebonyi states, have reported elevated levels of heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and chromium in rice mill effluents, with negative impacts on the health of local populations [5,6]. Despite Kebbi's prominence in rice production in Nigeria, there is still little scientific information on the effects of rice mill effluents on water quality in the state.

This study was therefore designed to assess the physicochemical properties, mineral elements and heavy metal concentrations in effluent and nearby drinking water sources from two rice mills in Birnin Kebbi. The findings will contribute valuable data for environmental protection, public health awareness, and policy formulation in Kebbi State.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area and Sample Collection

Birnin Kebbi, the capital city of Kebbi State in Northwestern Nigeria, is a rapidly developing urban centre and a major hub for agricultural activities. Located along the banks of the Sokoto River, the city serves as an administrative, commercial, and cultural centre for the State. Birnin Kebbi is located at approximately 12.4539°N, 4.1975°E. Its economy is predominantly agrarian, with rice farming and processing playing a vital role in its socio-economic development [7].

Effluent and drinking water samples were collected from two rice processing factories (EX and EY) located in different parts of Birnin Kebbi Metropolis to provide a representative overview of the environmental conditions associated with rice mill effluent discharge. Wastewater samples were obtained in triplicate from the effluent discharge

points and around the mills at different times of the day over five days, with one-day intervals between collections. Drinking water samples (DWX and DWY) were also collected in triplicate from sources located close to the discharge sites, following the method of [3]. All effluents samples were collected in sterilised plastic containers. On-site measurement of temperature, pH, conductivity and total dissolved solids were carried out immediately after collection. Sample intended for the determination of mineral elements and heavy metals were transported in tightly covered, sterilised plastic containers and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C until analysis [3].

2.2 Physicochemical Analysis

Water quality parameters were used to determine the physicochemical parameters of the collected water samples. To ensure accurate results, time-sensitive parameters, such as temperature, pH, and total dissolved solids (TDS), were measured on-site immediately after sample collection using a mercury-in-glass thermometer, a Pye Unicam pH meter, and an HM Digital TSS meter (Model TSS-4), respectively.

2.3 Heavy metal Analysis

The method of [8] was used for wet digestion. The entire wet digestion process was carried out in a fume cupboard for safety. Initially, 0.5 mL of each sample was taken into a 50 mL conical flask, and then 5 mL of nitric acid (HNO₃) was added which led to the formation of yellow fume mixture. The yellow fume disappeared after gentle heating for 2 minutes. Consequently, the mixture was allowed to cool for 30 minutes, thereafter 2.5 mL of perchloric acid (HClO₄) was added and heated until it became colourless. Lastly, 20 mL of distilled water was added to the heated samples and filtered into plastic bottles. The samples obtained were used for analysis using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS, Perkin Elmer PinAAcle 900H, USA).

2.4 Data Analysis

All results were presented as Mean ± standard deviation (SD) of triplicate determinations. Statistical comparisons were performed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVAs) in GraphPad Prism Software (version 8.0, GraphPad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Differences were considered statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

3.0 Results and Discussion

This study evaluated the physicochemical characteristics, elemental composition, and potential health risks associated with effluent wastewater and drinking water sources around two rice processing mills in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis. The results revealed notable variations in physicochemical parameters (Table 1), mineral elements (Table 2), and heavy metal concentrations (Table 3) of the collected water samples.

3.1 Physicochemical parameters

The elevated electrical conductivity (EC) and total dissolved solids (TDS) observed in effluent samples EX and EY indicate a substantial presence of dissolved salts, ions, and organic contaminants. These parameters are widely recognised as indicators of pollution, especially in industrial settings where untreated effluent discharges introduce high concentrations of chloride, phosphate, sulfate, and other ions into nearby water bodies. Elevated EC and TDS values in wastewater are often linked to poor industrial waste handling and inadequate treatment systems [9]. Similarly, [10] reported EC values exceeding 4000 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ and TDS levels above 2000 mg/L in effluents from rice and cassava processing plants in southeastern Nigeria, attributing these figures to the unregulated discharge of chemicals and organic residues. Such conditions not only reduce water quality but also pose ecological threats, including oxygen depletion and loss of aquatic biodiversity. Water with high EC and TDS is often unpalatable and may cause

gastrointestinal irritation, kidney stress, and increased risk of hypertension in individuals consuming it over long periods [11]. This underscores the importance of monitoring dissolved solids in drinking water near rice mills.

The variation in pH values observed across the sampled sites further highlight the influence of industrial effluents on water chemistry. In this study, EX displayed a wide pH range, spanning acidic to alkaline conditions, likely due to inconsistent effluent composition from rice processing activities, which may contain mixtures of organic waste, detergents, and other chemical residues. By contrast, EY maintained more stable pH values, generally neutral to slightly alkaline, possibly reflecting less variable effluent composition or relatively better on-site waste handling practices.

These observations align with the findings of [12], who reported fluctuating pH values (4.2-9.3) in untreated rice mill effluents in Southeastern Nigeria. They attributed this variability to the irregular discharge of both organic and inorganic waste streams without prior treatment. Unstable pH in receiving waters can create ecological stress, particularly affecting aquatic life, impair microbial activity, and alter metal solubility, thereby compounding the environmental impact of effluent discharges. Exposure to highly acidic or alkaline water may cause mucosal irritation, gastrointestinal disturbances, and corrosion of water distribution pipes, which can increase the leaching of toxic metals such as lead and copper into drinking water.

Table 1: Physicochemical parameters of effluents wastewater and drinking water from sources around two rice processing mills in Kebbi metropolis

Parameters	Samples			
	EX	DWX	EY	DWY
EC (S/m)	3932.00±538.54 ^a	294.20±18.42 ^b	2545.60±90.23 ^c	85.60±6.84 ^d
pH	6.29±1.82 ^a	7.38±1.37 ^a	7.86±0.38 ^a	5.81±0.53 ^a
TDS (mg/L)	1962.20±268.77 ^a	146.40±9.15 ^b	1268.80±40.29 ^c	43.00±3.08 ^d
Temp. (°C)	28.00±2.00 ^a	28.20±1.04 ^a	26.02±1.06 ^a	27.62±0.95 ^a

Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of five replicates. Values with different superscript letters indicate significant difference at $p < 0.05$. EX: Effluent wastewater from factory X; DWX: Drinking water from water sources around factory X; EY: Effluent wastewater from factory Y; DWY: Drinking water from water sources around factory Y. EC: Electrical conductivity (EC); pH: Degree of acidity or alkalinity; TDS: Total dissolved solids; Temp: Temperature.

3.2 Mineral elements

The analysis of macro-elements in the water samples revealed excessively high levels of potassium (K), particularly in EX (6042.33 mg/L) and EY (8175.00 mg/L), both of which drastically

exceeded the WHO guideline limit of 12 mg/L. Such extreme concentrations suggest a direct contamination from rice processing operations, likely through potash-based cleaning agents, fertiliser residues, and decomposing organic matter. This aligns with the findings of [13], who reported potassium concentrations above 5000 mg/L in

wastewater from agro-industrial zones. They attributed the elevated levels of potassium to residues from plant material and chemical additives.

Potassium contamination in drinking water poses a serious public health concern, particularly for individuals with kidney disorders or cardiovascular conditions. Excessive potassium intake can lead to hyperkalemia, a condition associated with irregular heart rhythms and, in severe cases, cardiac arrest [14].

Although calcium (Ca) and magnesium (Mg) levels in this study were within the WHO permissible limits, the elevated values at EX (Ca: 26.801 mg/L; Mg: 3.670 mg/L) compared to other sites raise concerns about cumulative exposure, particularly when combined with high TDS and EC values. Elevated levels of Ca and Mg, even when not immediately toxic, may contribute to water hardness, which affects both domestic water usage and the palatability of drinking water. Studies by [15] also suggest that elevated hardness can alter

the absorption of other essential trace elements and reduce the efficiency of water purification processes. While moderate water hardness is generally regarded as safe, epidemiological studies indicate that long-term consumption of very hard water may elevate the risk of kidney stone formation in susceptible individuals. Moreover, the mineral content in hard water can influence cardiovascular health, with current evidence suggesting that moderate hardness is neutral or potentially beneficial, whereas extreme levels may complicate certain preexisting conditions [16,17,18].

The findings in this study highlight a pattern of macro-element contamination that not only breaches safe thresholds, but also points to inadequate effluent treatment and poor environmental safeguards. Without urgent intervention, these levels may continue to rise, further degrading the quality of both surface and groundwater sources in Birnin Kebbi, with serious implications for public health.

Table 2: Levels of mineral elements in effluents wastewater and drinking water from two rice processing mills in Birnin Kebbi.

Elements	Samples				Recommended limits (WHO)
	EX	DWX	EY	DWY	
Ca	26.801±7.334 ^a	13.622±2.121 ^b	4.559±0.590 ^{b,c}	3.289±0.451 ^c	10-500
Fe	0.374±0.018 ^a	0.203±0.039 ^{b,c}	0.336±0.028 ^a	0.181±0.062 ^c	≤ 0.3
K	6042.333±5.503 ^a	95.727±2.889 ^b	8175.000±3.147 ^c	57.663±1.227 ^b	12.00
Mg	3.670±0.290 ^a	1.821±0.089 ^b	2.431±0.088 ^c	0.167±0.020 ^d	50
Mn	3.550±1.014 ^a	0.073±0.013 ^b	1.239±0.590 ^b	0.047±0.007 ^b	0.40
Na	182.400±0.173 ^a	5.570±0.282 ^b	54.307±3.982 ^c	10.782±0.513 ^d	200

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation of five replicates. Values with different superscript letters indicate significant difference at $p < 0.05$. EX: Effluent wastewater from factory X; DWX: Drinking water from water sources around factory X; EY: Effluent wastewater from factory Y; DWY: Drinking water from water sources around factory Y.

3.3 Heavy Metals

The presence of heavy metals, particularly lead (Pb) and chromium (Cr), at concentrations well above WHO permissible limits, underscores the severity of contamination in the studied water sources. In this study, Pb reached its highest concentration in EY (0.435 mg/L), while Cr peaked in EX (0.074 mg/L), both of which significantly exceed WHO's limits of 0.01 mg/L (Pb) and 0.05 mg/L (Cr). These elevated levels pose serious health threats, as both metals are known for their toxicity, bioaccumulation, and long-term health impacts.

These findings corroborate the work of [19], who identified similar levels of Pb and Cr in industrial effluents across southwestern Nigeria. Their study linked such contamination to poor waste disposal practices and associated these metals with neurological dysfunction, kidney damage, and developmental delays, particularly among children and pregnant women. Exposure to Cr (especially in its hexavalent form) has been documented to cause skin irritation, respiratory distress, and potential carcinogenic effects [20].

Furthermore, the detection of cadmium (Cd) in DWX and DWY at 0.0026 mg/L, though seemingly

low, still surpasses the ultralow WHO threshold of ≤ 0.002 mg/L. Its presence in drinking water sources raises concerns about leaching from industrial equipment, corroded pipes, or contaminated soils. Cd is a Group 1 carcinogen, and long-term exposure has been linked to bone demineralization, liver dysfunction, and increased cancer risk [21].

The elevated heavy metal concentrations in this study reflect broader national concerns over unregulated industrialization and lack of proper effluent monitoring. According to [22], the rapid growth of agro-processing industries in Nigeria without corresponding environmental controls is a major driver of water pollution in both rural and peri-urban communities.

Table 3: Heavy metals of effluents wastewater and drinking water from sources around two rice processing mills in Kebbi metropolis.

Elements	Samples				Recommended limits (WHO)
	EX	DWX	EY	DWY	
Cd	0.012±0.001 ^a	BDL	0.005±0.002 ^b	BDL	≤ 0.02
Cr	0.074±0.026 ^a	BDL	0.059±0.007 ^a	BDL	≤ 0.05
Cu	0.039±0.007 ^a	0.042±0.002 ^a	0.054±0.003 ^a	0.056±0.015 ^a	2.00
Pb	0.367±0.061 ^a	0.342±0.011 ^a	0.435±0.046 ^a	0.307±0.014 ^b	≤ 0.01
Zn	0.062±0.018 ^a	0.050±0.008 ^a	0.126±0.025 ^b	0.215±0.010 ^c	≤ 5.00

Values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation of five replicates. Values with different superscript letters indicate significant difference at $p < 0.05$. EX: Effluent wastewater from factory X; DWX: Drinking water from water sources around factory X; EY: Effluent wastewater from factory Y; DWY: Drinking water from water sources around factory Y.

4.0 Conclusion

This study revealed significant contamination of effluents and nearby drinking water sources from rice processing mills in Birnin Kebbi Metropolis. Physicochemical parameters, particularly electrical conductivity (EC) and total dissolved solids (TDS), were markedly elevated in EX and EY, indicating high levels of dissolved salts and organic pollutants in the industrial discharge. Mineral element analysis showed extreme potassium concentrations, well above WHO guidelines, alongside elevated manganese, sodium, and iron, all of which contribute to poor water quality and potential health risks. Heavy metals especially lead (Pb), chromium (Cr), and cadmium (Cd) exceeded the WHO permissible limits in both effluents and adjacent drinking water sources (DWX and DWY), highlighting the severity of contamination and the threat of long-term health impacts such as kidney damage, neurological disorders, cardiovascular complications, and cancer.

The findings underscore the urgent need for effective wastewater management, regular monitoring of drinking water sources, and strict enforcement of environmental regulations. Strengthening public health awareness, investing in effluent treatment infrastructure, and promoting sustainable industrial practices are critical steps to safeguard water resources, protect community health, and ensure environmental sustainability in

Kebbi State and similar agro-industrial regions of Nigeria.

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